

Behavior of the thermo-physical properties and performance evaluation of the refrigerants blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) for cooling cycle

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ABSTRACT

Blends have gained special interest recently where they can integrate the advantages of the single-fluid and may achieve excellent thermophysical properties and environmental characteristics also a better coefficient of performance. The pure refrigerant R134a commonly used in the vapor compression cycle of the cooling systems will be phased out due to its high global warming potential, while refrigerant blends of Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon are considered as a potential alternative owing to their excellent environmental characteristics. In this study, the thermodynamic properties and performance evaluation of the blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) were investigated. In the first section, the thermodynamic properties of the refrigerant blends: R134a+R600a, R134a+R290, R1234yf+R290 and R1234ze(E)+R600a are determined with the thermodynamic model : “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” which consists of the Peng–Robinson equation of state, the Mathias–Copeman alpha function and the Wong–Sandler mixing rules requiring the NRTL model. In the second section, the performances of binary refrigerant systems as substitutes to pure refrigerant R134a in single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle were analyzed for the condensation temperature of 50 °C and evaporating temperatures ranging between -10 °C and 10 °C. The results presented that our thermodynamic model could describe the vapor-liquid equilibria characteristics of blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon), where it had the highest accuracy, with the relative deviation of 1.17 % and 0.74 % for liquid and vapor mole fractions, respectively. On another hand, the performance parameters of the refrigerant blends were analyzed where the present results showed that the performance of blend R1234yf+R290 exhibited the highest performance in terms of specific cooling capacity, coefficient of performance and environmental protection compared to other blends.

1 Introduction

Developing new refrigerants with high energy efficiency and low environmental impacts is one of the highest challenges of the refrigeration sector. Since it is very hard to find appropriate pure substance to replace the traditional refrigerants that can meet the requirements of environmental performance, thermo-physical properties, safety and cycle performance at the same time.

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Most of the refrigerants currently used in the cooling systems are hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs) and hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), which have either a high global warming potential (GWP) or an ozone depression potential (ODP). According to the Montreal (Ozone layer protection) and Kyoto protocols (Climate protection) those substances will be phased out because they great impact on the environment [1], where fluorinated greenhouse gases with GWP higher than 150 will no longer be used in cooling systems.

In recent years, several hydrofluoroolefins (HFOs) [2] have been projected as the replacement for the existing HFCs refrigerants like R134a (1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane) owing to their environmental performance where are considered to be a potential next generation refrigerants (Fig.1) [3]. Among those HFOs, R1234yf (2,3,3,3-tetrafluoroprop-1-ene) and R1234ze(E) (trans-1,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-1-propene) fluids with zero ODP and low GWP have been considered as one of the most promising candidates of HFCs in cooling systems. However, as a pure fluid, R1234yf and R1234ze(E) has several drawbacks, such as mildly flammability [4, 5], smaller latent heat in evaporator and condenser, which results in lower cooling capacity and coefficient of performance than R134a in series tests [5, 6].

On another hand, we can find that hydrocarbon (HCs) refrigerants like Isobutane (R600a) and Propane (R290) presents several benefits [7]: a good performance, excellent thermodynamic properties, zero ODP, low GWP, no fluorine, high latent heat of vaporization and easy availability, but there existed potential safety hazards in applications owing to their flammable and explosive properties which pose another problem which must be solved.

Fig. 1 –Advancements in refrigerants [8]

One of the proposed solutions to improve the characteristic of pure refrigerants is to blend those fluids between them to can compensate for the low safety, poor cycle performance using the principle of complementary advantages.

In the mechanical vapor compression cycle, refrigerant mixtures like the binary or ternary systems become the most promising type of alternative refrigerants due to the high coefficient performance and the excellent environmental characteristics [9, 10]. Consequently, the mixture of two or three refrigerants (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon for instance) may give the opportunity to overcome the above concern.

In this context, binary systems R134a+R600a, R134a+R290, R1234yf+R290 and R1234ze(E)+R600a consist of a combination of pure refrigerants selected from hydrocarbon (R600a and R290) and fluorocarbon (R134a, R1234yf and R1234ze(E)). Fluorocarbon and Hydrocarbon refrigerant are included among them in order to cut down the problem of cycle performance, environmental performance, thermophysical properties, and safety at the same time and to produce a new refrigerant with good thermo-physical properties and performance characteristics similar to those of pure refrigerant R134a.

Therefore, the binary refrigerant has a good potential to be applied in the cooling system. Indeed, the accurate knowledge of thermo-physical properties, especially thermodynamic properties of a refrigerant is essential to the optimum design and the investigation of their performance in the vapor compression refrigeration cycle. However, data concerning these refrigerant mixtures are very scarce, where there are limited researches, which focused on this type of refrigerant in both thermo-physical properties and performance evaluation in the literature review [11].

The present work aims to explore the thermophysical properties of refrigerants blends of fluorocarbon/hydrocarbon above, especially the fluid-phase behavior using a thermodynamic model where we are going emphasis in two section on

the behavior of the thermodynamic characteristics of this type of mixtures and their performance evaluation with the single-fluid R134a in the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle.

In the first section, the thermodynamic behavior of refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) was investigated by the combination of the cubic equation of state (the Peng–Robinson equation of state associated with the Mathias–Copeman alpha function) with excess free energy model (the NRTL model), using the Wong–Sandler mixing rule.

In the second section, based on the behavior of binary refrigerant systems established in the first section, the cycle performances of mixtures were analyzed and compared with those of R134a fluid which has high global warming potential (GWP=1430) [12].

The values of physical and environmental data of the compounds of the studied refrigerant blends are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 - Physical and environmental properties of the compositions of refrigerant blends [12-17]

Properties	R134a	R290	R1234yf	R600a	R1234ze(E)
Type	HFC	HC	HFO	HC	HFO
Molecular structure					
Chemical structure					
Molecular formula	CF ₃ CH ₂ F	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₃	CF ₃ CF=CH ₂	C ₄ H ₁₀	CHF=CHCF ₃
CAS number	811-97-2	74-98-6	754-12-1	75-28-5	29118-24-9
Molar mass (kg/kmol)	102.03	44.096	114.04	58.122	114.04
Critical temperature (K)	374.21	369.89	367.85	407.85	382.51
Critical pressure (MPa)	4.0593	4.2512	3.3823	3.6400	3.6349
GWP	1430	3	4	3	6
ODP	0	0	0	0	0

2 Establishment of thermodynamic model

The thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” (Fig.2) is used to describe the behavior of the thermodynamic properties of the refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon).

Fig. 2 – Correlative thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL”

The model consists by the combination of the Peng–Robinson (Peng and Robinson, 1976) [18] equation of state, with the Mathias–Copeman (Mathias and Copeman, 1983) [19] alpha function and the Wong–Sandler [20] (Wong and Sandler, 1992) mixing rules involving NRTL (Renon and Prausnitz, 1968) model [21].

2.1 Equations of state

Peng–Robinson equation of state (PR-EoS) is one of the most convenient model to predict and correlate the phase behavior of fluids, where it is widely used in the industrial fields to describe the thermo-physical property of fluids especially the behavior of the thermodynamic properties, so we have chosen this equation in this work.

The (PR-EoS) [18] can be written as follows:

$$P = \frac{RT}{v-b} - \frac{a\alpha(T)}{(v^2 + 2bv - b^2)} \quad (1)$$

With:

$$a = 0.457240 \frac{R^2 T_c^2}{P_c} \quad (2)$$

$$b = 0.07780 \frac{RT_c}{P_c} \quad (3)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, v the molar volume, P the pressure, T the temperature, T_c and P_c are the critical temperature and critical pressure of pure fluids, a and b are parameters of (PR-EoS), respectively.

The values of critical temperature T_c and critical pressure P_c for each pure refrigerant are listed in Table 1.

2.2 Alpha function

The Mathias–Copeman (MC) alpha function [19] is given by :

$$\alpha(T) = \left[1 + c_1 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{T}{T_c}} \right) + c_2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{T}{T_c}} \right)^2 + c_3 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{T}{T_c}} \right)^3 \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

If $T > T_c$

$$\alpha(T) = \left[1 + c_1 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{T}{T_c}} \right) \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

Where c_1 , c_2 and c_3 are the three adjustable parameters of the Mathias–Copeman equation.

Table 2 - Mathias–Copeman coefficients of the compositions of refrigerant blends [13]

Compound	c_1	c_2	c_3
R134a	0.8497	0.0065	-0.0535
R1234ze(E)	0.8767	-0.7751	3.0689
R1234yf	0.8293	-0.8477	3.4559
R600a	0.6524	-0.1493	0.5992
R290	0.6000	-0.0006	0.1738

2.3 Mixing rules

We applied the (PR-EoS) to the refrigerant blends by using the Wong–Sandler (WS) [20] mixing rules for both vapor and liquid phases. The Wong–Sandler mixing rules are chosen here from the good representation of vapor–liquid equilibria (VLE) of blends:

$$b = \frac{\sum_i \sum_j x_i x_j \left(b - \frac{a}{RT} \right)}{1 - \left(\frac{\sum_i x_i \frac{a_i}{b_i}}{RT} + \frac{g_\gamma^E(T, P = \infty, x)}{CRT} \right)}$$

(6)

$$b - \frac{a}{RT} = \sum_i \sum_j x_i x_j \left(b - \frac{a}{RT} \right)_{ij} \quad (7)$$

With

$$\left(b - \frac{a}{RT} \right)_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(b - \frac{a}{RT} \right)_i + \left(b - \frac{a}{RT} \right)_j \right] (1 - k_{ij}) \quad (8)$$

Where k_{ij} is an adjustable binary interaction parameter and C a numerical constant depends on the (PR-EoS).

2.4 NRTL model

The component activity parameters of refrigerant blends are calculated with (NRTL model). The NRTL equation was derived by Renon and Prausnitz [21] for fluid phase activity coefficients using the Non-Randomness assumption and Scott's Two-Liquid theory.

The NRTL formula for the activity coefficient is:

$$\ln \gamma_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \tau_{ji} G_{ji} x_j}{\sum_{k=1}^n G_{ki} x_k} + \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{x_j G_{ij}}{\sum_{k=1}^n G_{ki} x_k} \left(\tau_{ij} - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n x_k \tau_{kj} G_{kj}}{\sum_{k=1}^n G_{ki} x_k} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$G_{ij} = \exp\left(-\alpha_{ji} \frac{\tau_{ji}}{RT}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{ii} = \tau_{jj} = 0 \quad (11)$$

The excess Gibbs energy model chosen is the NRTL local composition model [21] is:

$$g^E = \sum_i x_i \sum_j \frac{x_j \exp\left(-\alpha_{ji} \frac{\tau_{ji}}{RT}\right)}{\sum_k x_k \exp\left(-\alpha_{ki} \frac{\tau_{ki}}{RT}\right)} \tau_{ji} \quad (12)$$

Where α_{ji} , τ_{ji} and τ_{ij} are adjustable parameters. In this work, $\alpha_{ij} = 0.3$.

To prove the accuracy of our thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” used in this study, the calculated results of the thermodynamic properties are compared with experimental data from the literature, where the deviations MRDU and the BIASU are applied on mole fractions of liquid and vapor phase for the refrigerant blends considered in this work.

These indicators are defined respectively by Eqs.(13) and (14) [22]:

$$\text{BIASU} = \left(\frac{100}{N}\right) \sum \left(\frac{U_{\text{cal}} - U_{\text{exp}}}{U_{\text{exp}}}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{MRDU} = \left(\frac{100}{N}\right) \sum \left| \frac{U_{\text{cal}} - U_{\text{exp}}}{U_{\text{exp}}} \right| \quad (14)$$

Where N is the number of data points, and $U=x_1$ or y_1 .

3 Behavior of thermodynamic and environmental properties of study blends

3.1 Thermodynamic properties

The thermodynamic properties are the most important factors that should be considered to fulfil the requirements of cooling system performance. In this section, we present the thermodynamic properties obtained of the refrigerant blends using the thermodynamic model proposed above.

Figs.3-6 illustrate the variation of bubble point pressure and dew point pressure of the refrigerant binary systems: R134a+R290, R1234yf+R290, R1234ze(E)+R600a and R134a+R600a, respectively at different temperature where the symbol curves denote the experimental data of vapor-liquid equilibria properties (P,T,x,y) of the literature while the dashed line curves shows the calculated values obtained using our thermodynamic model: “PR-MC-WS-NRTL”.

Fig. 3 – Behavior of the thermodynamic properties (P, T, x, y) of R134a+R290 system: Experimental data [14]: (●) 255 K ; (▲) 265 K ; (■) 275 K ; (◆) 285 K ; (▲) Azeotropic point; (...): Azeotropic line; (...): Calculated values using “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model

Fig. 4 –Behavior of the thermodynamic properties (P, T, x, y) of R1234yf+R290 system: Experimental data [15]:(■) 253.15 K ; (●) 263.15 K ; (◆) 273.15 K ; (▲) 283.15 K ; (□) 293.15 K ; (▲) Azeotropic point; (...): Azeotropic line; (...): Calculated values using “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model

Fig. 5 – Behavior of the thermodynamic properties (P, T, x, y) of R1234ze(E)+R600a system:

Experimental data [16]: (▲) 258.15 K; (◆) 268.15 K; (■) 278.15 K; (●) 288.15 K; (▲) Azeotropic point; (...) Azeotropic line; (...): Calculated values using our thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model

Fig. 6 – Behavior of the thermodynamic properties (P, T, x, y) of R134a+R600a system: Experimental data [17]: (◆) 293.66 K; (▲) 303.68 K; (▲) Azeotropic point; (...) Azeotropic line; (...): Calculated values using “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model

The vapor-liquid equilibria data (P,T,x,y) of these blends have been studied in a temperature interval which corresponds to: 4 isotherms for R134a+R290 (255;265;275;285) K and R1234ze(E)+R600a (258.15;268.15;278.15;288.15) K, 5 isotherms for R1234yf+R290 (253.15; 263.15; 273.15;283.15; 293.15) K and 2 isotherms for R134a+R600a (293.66 ;303.68) K and it is found that the calculated results are in good agreement with the experimental data (the relative deviation of liquid and vapor mole fractions is less than 1.17 % and 0.74 %, respectively (see Table 3-6)). From the phase diagrams of the corresponding binary systems, we can see that the studied refrigerant blends exhibits an azeotropic behavior for all the temperature range studied (the bubble and dew curve are tangent to each other and these two curves do not intersect), where the composition of the liquid phase and the composition of the vapor phase are identical ($x_1=y_1$). It can be found obviously from these diagrams that an azeotropic behavior is observed between the mole fractions (0.2 and 0.4) for both binary mixtures: R134a+R290 and R1234yf+R290 in the temperature range between 255 to 285 K and 253.15 to 293.15 K, respectively. Whereas for the binary systems: R1234ze(E)+R600a and R134a+R600a, the azeotropic behavior is observed between the mole fractions (0.6 and 0.7) and (0.7 and 0.8), in a temperature interval 258.15-288.15 K and 293.66-303.68 K, respectively. Furthermore, the studied refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) evaporates and condenses as a single substance at azeotropic behavior, and it does not have the glide temperature problem which is the temperature difference between the dew point and bubble temperatures at a given pressure and composition, which we can consider as a potential alternative refrigerants.

Table 3 - Relative deviation MRDU and BIASU obtained in fitting experimental data with “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model for R134a+R290 system

<i>T/K</i>	<i>BIAS x %</i>	<i>MRD x %</i>	<i>BIAS y %</i>	<i>MRD y %</i>
255	0.51	0.76	0.36	0.36
265	0.96	0.96	0.31	0.35
275	0.41	0.65	0.15	0.19
285	0.49	0.61	-0.08	0.24

Table 4 - Relative deviation MRDU and BIASU obtained in fitting experimental data with “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model for R1234yf+R290 system

<i>T/K</i>	<i>BIAS x %</i>	<i>MRD x %</i>	<i>BIAS y %</i>	<i>MRD y %</i>
253.15	1.17	0.78	0.24	0.66
263.15	1.12	1.75	0.66	0.78
273.15	0.37	0.98	-0.17	0.76
283.15	0.34	0.83	-0.08	0.57

293.15	-0.84	1.24	-0.99	1.08
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Table 5 - Relative deviation MRDU and BIASU obtained in fitting experimental data with “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model for R1234ze (E)+R600a system

<i>T/K</i>	<i>BIAS x %</i>	<i>MRD x %</i>	<i>BIAS y %</i>	<i>MRD y %</i>
258.15	-0.01	0.32	-0.32	0.47
268.15	-0.22	0.39	-0.41	0.51
278.15	-0.14	0.22	-0.17	0.50
288.15	-0.26	0.36	-0.25	0.62

Table 6 - Relative deviation MRDU and BIASU obtained in fitting experimental data with “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” model for R134a+R600a system

<i>T/K</i>	<i>BIAS x %</i>	<i>MRD x %</i>	<i>BIAS y %</i>	<i>MRD y %</i>
293.66	-0.75	0.89	-0.74	0.74
303.68	-0.16	0.16	-0.36	0.53

3.2 Environmental properties

To research new refrigerants by using an alternative refrigerant blend that gives a suitable system performance the similar as the existing refrigerant R134a in mechanical vapor compression system, the environmental properties should be considered. Therefore, to be regarded the refrigerants blends as a low GWP refrigerant, the GWP upper limit of 150 must adopted.

The next stage involved evaluating the environmental aspects of refrigerant blends and compare it with the single fluid R134a.

The mixture GWP is estimated based on the following equation [10]:

$$GWP_{mixture} = \sum_i^n w_i * GWP_i \quad (15)$$

Where w_i , represents the mass fraction of component i in refrigerant blends.

Table 7 - Environmental characteristics of the studied refrigerants

<i>Refrigerants</i>	<i>Mass fraction</i>	<i>GWP</i>	<i>ODP</i>
R134a+R290	0.35/0.65	502.45	0
R134a+R600a	0.76/0.24	1086.87	0
R1234ze(E)+R600a	0.63/0.37	4.89	0
R1234yf+R290	0.36/0.64	3.36	0
R134a	/	1430	0

Table 7 shows the environmental characteristic calculation of the studied refrigerants considered in the present work. As we can see from the above table, the blends R1234ze(E)+R600a and R1234yf+R290 exhibits a GWP lower than 150, while for blends R134a+R290 and R134a+R600a, the GWP is higher than 150, which allows us to say that the refrigerant blends R1234ze(E)+R600a and R1234yf+R290 can be recommended as the replacing refrigerant of single fluid R134a which has high global warming potential (GWP=1430).

The simulation of the mechanical vapor compression system operation using the refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) will be discussed in the next section.

4 Cooling cycle and performance evaluation

4.1 Single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle

Fig.7 shows the configuration and the corresponding Temperature-Entropy (T-s) diagram of the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle. The cycle consists of a compressor, condenser, expansion device and evaporator. The different cycle processes can be explained as follows: process (1→2) is a compression through the compressor, process (2→3) is a heat rejected to ambient in the condenser, process (3→4) is an expansion through the expansion device, process (4→1) is a heat absorbed from conditioned space in the evaporator.

Fig. 7 – Single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle [23]

The cycle it works as follows: the saturating vapor of the refrigerant is compressed at high pressure in the compressor up to pressure P_2 thus passing to the superheated state (state 2), then it is condensed at high temperature T_3 in the condenser (state 3) by heat transfer to the ambient. The refrigerant pressure is reduced through an expansion device to bring it to a state of low pressure (state 4). At pressure P_4 and temperature T_4 , the refrigerant vaporizes, which extracts heat from the conditioned space where it produces cold. To complete the cycle, at the evaporator outlet (state 1), the vapor saturating of the refrigerant at low pressure is sucked in and brought to high pressure by the compressor.

In order to simplify the calculation to simulate the performance of the cooling cycle using refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) the following assumptions are made:

- The pressure drop is negligible in the evaporator, the condenser and the connecting tubes;
- The refrigerants at the evaporator and the condenser outlet is in saturation conditions;
- The variations in kinetic and potential energy are not considerable;
- The transformations in the heat exchangers are isobaric process ($p = \text{constant}$);
- The flow through in the expansion device is isenthalpic process ($h = \text{constant}$);
- The compression in the compressor is isentropic process ($s = \text{constant}$).

With these assumptions, the mathematical model for the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle can be established as follows:

At the evaporator outlet:

$$h_1 = f(T_e, x = 1)$$

(16)

$$p_1 = f(T_e, x = 1)$$

(17)

$$s_1 = f(T_e, x = 1)$$

(18)

$$\rho_1 = f(T_e, x = 1)$$

(19)

At the condenser outlet:

$$h_3 = f(T_c, x = 0)$$

(20)

$$p_3 = f(T_c, x = 0)$$

(21)

At the compressor outlet:

$$s_2 = s_1$$

(22)

$$p_2 = p_3$$

(23)

$$h_{2is} = f(s_2, p_2)$$

(24)

At the expansion device outlet:

$$h_4 = h_3 \tag{25}$$

Then, the specific work (W_{comp}) and the specific cooling capacity (q_{evap}) of the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle are defined by Eqs. (26) and (27), respectively:

$$W_{comp} = (h_{2is} - h_1) \tag{26}$$

$$q_{evap} = (h_1 - h_4) \tag{27}$$

The volumetric refrigerating capacity (VRC) of the cycle is given as:

$$VRC = \frac{(h_1 - h_4)}{\rho_1} \tag{28}$$

Where ρ_1 is the density of the refrigerant at the exit of evaporator.

The COP of the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle is determined by the following relation:

$$COP = \frac{q_{evap}}{W_{comp}} \tag{29}$$

4.2 Cycle performance

4.2.1 Validation

Before presenting the results, a brief discussion on the validation of the simulation program for the vapor compression refrigeration system would be appropriate. The present numerical model is verified with the test results data available of Dalkilic and Wongwises [24] using R22 as the working fluid with the same operating conditions (evaporation temperatures vary from -10 to 10 °C and the constant condensation temperature of 50 °C).

Fig. 8 – Validation of the simulation model

From the Fig.8, it was observed that present work results of the COP of refrigerant R22 for various evaporator temperatures (-10 to 10 °C) exhibit good agreement with literature results, which confirms the validity of our simulation model.

4.2.2 Performance parameters

The following section presents the results of the comparative evaluation of refrigerant blends: R134a+R600a, R134a+R290, R1234yf+R290 and R1234ze(E)+R600a with R134a in the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle, where we investigated various performance parameters of refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) for different evaporator temperatures.

Fig. 9 – Effect of evaporating temperature on the specific cooling capacity

Fig. 10 – Effect of evaporating temperature on the volumetric refrigeration capacity

Fig. 11 – Effect of evaporating temperature on the volumetric refrigeration capacity

Fig.9 depict the results of the effect of evaporating temperature (-10 to 10 °C) on the specific cooling capacity of the investigating refrigerants (R134a, R134a+R290, R134a+R600a, R1234ze(E)+R600a and R1234yf+R290) in the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle. From this figure, it was noted that an increase in the evaporation temperature leads to an increase in specific cooling capacity for each fluids. The results showed that the specific cooling capacity of the blends: R1234yf+R290 and R134a+R290 are higher compared to the other studied fluids. When the evaporation temperature increases from -10 to 10 °C, the specific cooling capacity of the booth mixtures increases from 168.85 to 187.182 kJ/kg and 167.413 to 184.725 kJ/kg, respectively. In addition, it was observed that the maximum values of the specific cooling capacity of the cycle working with the refrigerant blends (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon): R1234yf+R290, R134a+R290, R1234ze(E)+R600a and R134a+R600a is better than the obtained with the single fluid R134a which has a specific cooling capacity varied from 121.041 to 132.695 kJ/kg.

The effect of evaporating temperature on the volumetric refrigeration capacity is displayed in Fig.10. It indicates the size of compressor required in order to produce a desired cooling effect. As clearly shown in figure, it is noticed that the volumetric refrigeration capacity increases also with an increase in evaporator temperature for all the considered

refrigerants. Since the increase in volumetric capacity depends on both the values of vapor density and cooling effect of fluids.

It is evident that the volumetric refrigeration capacity of the two blends: R134a+R290 and R1234yf+R290 are the highest among four studied blends and it are very high to that of the volumetric refrigeration capacity of R134a fluid.

Fig.11 shows the effect of evaporating temperature on the coefficient of performance (COP) of refrigerant blends and the single fluid R134a. As shown in the figure, like the specific cooling capacity and the volumetric refrigeration capacity, the COP increases as the evaporator temperature increases for all investigating refrigerants. From the curves of the variation of the COP, it was noticed that the maximum COP of the single-stage vapor compression refrigeration cycle, which working with the both blends R1234ze(E)+R600a and R1234yf+R290 is better than the obtained with R134a+R290 and R134a+R600a. Additionally, it was found that the values of the COP of R1234ze(E)+R600a were similar to R1234yf+R290.

5 Conclusion

In overall, the present work is devoted to the thermodynamic and energetic study of refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon). First, the behavior of the thermodynamic properties of the refrigerant blends was studied with the thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” composed of the Peng–Robinson equation of state (PR-EoS), using the Mathias–Copeman (MC) alpha function and the Wong–Sandler (WS) mixing rules involving NRTL model.

Secondly, the performance parameters of refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) as alternatives to single fluid R134a were investigated theoretically in a standard vapor compression cycle for cooling system at the evaporation temperatures vary from -10 to 10 °C and the constant condensation temperature of 50 °C.

From the thermodynamic behavior and performance computation of various refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The studied refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon) exhibits a azeotropic behavior for all the temperature range studied;
- A good agreement is obtained between the results of our work obtained with the thermodynamic model “PR-MC-WS-NRTL” and the sets of literature data, where it confirms that the observed VLE data satisfy the thermodynamic consistency;
- Compared with the pure R134a refrigerant, the two mixtures: R1234ze(E)+R600a and R1234yf+R290 yielded a GWP lower than 150;
- The specific cooling capacity of the blends: R1234yf+R290 and R134a+R290 was higher among R134a+R600a, R1234ze(E)+R600a and the single fluid R134a;
- The blends R134a+R290 and R1234yf+R290 has obvious advantages in terms of volumetric refrigeration capacity compared to R134a fluid;
- The COP of refrigerant blends R1234yf+R290 and R1234ze(E)+R600a was higher among R134a+R600a, R134a+R290.

By analyzing the consideration above of refrigerant blends of (Fluorocarbon/Hydrocarbon), R1234yf+R290 yields better advantages, which confirms that it could be a good suitable substitute for refrigeration systems. Because of these features it may be may be beneficial to further look into this blend in future studies.

NOMENCLATURE

List of symbols

- a* Energy parameter in the PR–EoS ($\text{J m}^3 \text{mol}^{-2}$)
b Molar co-volume parameter in the PR–EoS ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
C Numerical constant equal to -0.62323
c₁, c₂, c₃ Mathias–Copeman coefficient
G Gibbs energy (J)
g Molar Gibbs energy (J mol^{-1})
N Number of experimental points
P Pressure (MPa or kPa)
R Universal gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
T Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ or K)
v Molar volume ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
x Molar fraction of liquid phase
y Molar fraction of vapor phase
k_{ij} Binary interaction parameter
h Specific enthalpy (kJ kg^{-1})
s Specific entropy ($\text{kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
q Specific cooling capacity (kJ kg^{-1})
w Specific work (kJ kg^{-1})
x Vapor quality

Greek letters

- $\alpha(T)$ Alpha function
 γ_i Activity coefficient of component *i*
 ∞ Infinite pressure reference state
 τ_{ij} Binary interaction parameter of NRTL model
 a_{ij} NRTL model parameter

ρ Density (kg m^{-3})

Subscripts

- i, j, k* Molecular species
cal Calculated
exp Experimental
mixture Mixture
C Condensing process
c Critical property
comp Compressor
e Evaporation process
evap Evaporator
is Isentropic process
 1-4 State point

Superscripts

E Excess property

Abbreviations

- COP Coefficient of performance
 VRC Volumetric refrigeration capacity
 GWP Global warming potential
 ODP Ozone depleting potential
 EoS Equation of state
 PR Peng–Robinson
 MC Mathias–Copeman
 WS Wong–Sandler
 NRTL Non-Random Two Liquids
 VLE Vapor liquid equilibria

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